

THE GEOLOGY OF THE BATTLE OF VIMY RIDGE

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INTRODUCTION:

Every November 11th we commemorate Remembrance Day, which provides a solemn moment to unite in honoring the tremendous sacrifices of our fallen soldiers, including the 3,598 Canadians killed in the Battle of Vimy Ridge, which took place from April 9 to April 12, 1917, during the First World War (WWI). Located in northern France, Vimy Ridge was a formidable stretch of high ground that had been under German control since 1914. Its strategic importance lay in its commanding view of the surrounding landscape, which made it a natural fortress for those who held it. This battle was a part of the broader British-led Arras Offensive, which aimed to break through the formidable German defensive lines in the region (Figure 1). For the first time all four Canadian divisions attacked together: soldiers from all regions of Canada were present at the battle. Brigadier-General A.E. Ross declared after the war, “in those few minutes I witnessed the birth of a nation.” The Battle of Vimy Ridge would go on to become one of Canada’s most celebrated military victories (Foot, 2006).

FIGURE 1: Geological map of the area surrounding the Vimy Ridge. The red dashed line shows the location of the Western Front in 1917. Vimy Ridge is shown with a red star. Geologic map sourced from infoterre.brgm.fr.

The significance of Vimy Ridge extended beyond its military fortifications. Previous attempts by French and British forces to capture it had resulted in heavy casualties and ultimate failure (Gendzwill, 2007). The ridge symbolized the deadlock of trench warfare on the Western Front, with fortified positions and intricate defensive networks, making any advance a perilous endeavor. It was under these circumstances that the Canadian Corps, under the leadership of General Julian Byng and General Arthur

Currie, launched their meticulously planned and innovative assault on Vimy Ridge. This battle ultimately proved to be a turning point in World War I, showcasing the potential for victory in an otherwise brutal and stagnant conflict. This article examines the crucial role that geology played in the battle, from the presence of the ridge itself, to the preparations, execution, and even the battle’s ultimate memorialization.

FIGURE 2: Original cross section from T.W. Edgeworth David, made during preparations for the battle. The black dotted box shows the approximate interval described in Figure 3. Modified from nla.gov.au.

GEOLOGIC BACKGROUND:

The Western Front of WWI was largely static in 1917 (Figure 1). WWI saw a dramatic increase in the accuracy and efficiency of artillery and machine gun fire, which reduced the effectiveness of offensive frontal assaults by infantry (Doyle, 2014). In response, both sides placed increased emphasis on defensive positions. The topography of the land then became extremely significant to the outcome of the war, as the high ground controlled the efficacy of defensive positions. Some authors have argued that the Western Front of WWI was essentially a war fought over topographic positions (Doyle, 2014). As a result, geology became a key strategic component of the war. Everything from river morphologies, structural features, and substrate composition needed to be factored into battle plans. The impact of geology became especially apparent when considering subsurface conditions during military mining operations.

Each of the opponents recognized the importance of geoscience to the operation and so appointed geological staff and advisors. The Germans had the initial advantage, having gained ground early in the conflict, and had set up defensive positions in high ground wherever possible. They set up a large geological staff, and even found extensive geological information within the occupied city of Lille (Doyle, 2014). The Allies appointed Major (later Lieutenant Colonel) T.W. Edgeworth David to focus on military mining and dugout construction,

FIGURE 3: Stratigraphic chart showing the original informal stratigraphic divisions from T.W. Edgeworth David on the right, shown in italics. This is shown adjacent to our interpreted connection to the modern stratigraphic column of the area. Also illustrated are the dominant fracture patterns within the Lewes Nodular Chalk Formation and the Seaford Chalk Formation. Grey boxes show the relative stratigraphic position of common excavations.

FIGURE 4: Plan of attack for Vimy Ridge that shows the topography of the ridge, which was an important part of the battle plan. Large arrows added for emphasis. Of note is the area referred to as "The Pimple", which is visible to the north of the area assigned to the 4th Division (small purple arrow). The Pimple was the final part of Vimy Ridge to be captured by the Allies. Image credit: Drawn by the Dominion Bureau of Statistics, printed by Geographical Section, General Staff, Department of National Defence - Library and Archives Canada does not allow free use of its copyrighted works. See Category:Images from Library and Archives Canada., Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=4174127>.

and Lieutenant (later Captain) W.B.R. King to focus on water supply (Doyle, 2014). T.W. Edgeworth David constructed the geologic cross section of Vimy Ridge, shown in Figure 2. Modern stratigraphic divisions have since been created for this area, and our interpreted correlation and reconciliation with modern stratigraphy is shown in Figure 3.

Geology of the Vimy Ridge area comprises a thin layer of weathered silt and clay overlying Cretaceous chinks. These chinks at Vimy Ridge are equivalent to the icon chalk cliffs found in Southern England, which are perhaps the most famous chalk deposits in the world. These were deposited in the Late Cretaceous epoch on a submerged continental shelf in water depths between 100-300 m (Tucker and Wright, 1990). In this region of France, the chalk reaches a thickness of approximately 200 m, and contains interbedded layers of clay-rich marl, bioturbated nodular chalk, hardgrounds, and flint seams. These variations contribute to variable porosity, permeability, and geomechanical properties. At Vimy Ridge, the mining and excavations were located primarily within the Seaford Chalk and Lewes Chalk. While there was lots of internal variability within the chinks, they were collectively soft enough to allow for subterranean mining operations.

The Lewes and Seaford chinks are primarily comprised of coccoliths, with lesser amounts of planktonic foraminifera and calcispheres. Macrofossils common within the shallower facies include echinoids, sponges, bivalves, bryozoans, and brachiopods. Deeper-water chalk facies feature belemnites, ammonites, and crinoids as the most common macrofossils (Tucker and Wright, 1990). Trace fossils are also common, with *Thalassinoides*, *Chondrites*, *Zoophycos*, and *Planolites* being the most commonly reported (White, 2007).

The topography at Vimy Ridge consists of gently folded Upper Cretaceous chinks disconformably overlain by Paleogene sediments. The Somme region is part of the larger Weald-Boulonnais anticlinorium that reaches all the way into southern England, creating regionally pervasive northwest-southeast trending structures (White, 2007). Vimy ridge itself is one of these structures, a ridge created by the Marqueffles fault. It's a NW-SE trending normal fault, creating a 9 km long ridge with approximately 100m in elevation (Figure 4), with a smaller adjoining hill to the NW referred to as "The Pimple". Characterizing the ridge itself was an important part of developing the battle plan. As such, highly dangerous aerial reconnaissance was even used to take photographs to better analyze the topography and exposed geological structures (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5: Aerial reconnaissance aircraft taking photographs of the topography below. The camera apparatus can be seen in black below his right hand. This photograph Q 33850 comes from the collections of the Imperial War Museums., Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=632051>.

INFLUENCE OF GEOLOGY ON MILITARY EXCAVATIONS:

Geology was a major contributing factor to excavating and mining efforts throughout WWI. This was especially true at Vimy Ridge. As discussed, the relatively soft rock allowed for extensive excavating and tunneling on both sides. Allied excavations at Vimy Ridge included trenches, subways, dugouts, and fighting tunnels (Figure 6). The tunnels were constructed secretly, with a total of 11 subways, totalling approximately 6 km in length. Many of these extended from the rear areas to deliver troops, artillery, and supplies to the battlefield ahead of "no man's land" (Foot, 2006).

Subways were constructed at depths between 10 and 20 m below ground to target the most geomechanically favorable stratigraphy wherever possible. These needed around 16 m of rock overhead to protect troops against heavy artillery (Deiderichs and Hutchinson, 2020). To prevent roof collapse, the width of the tunnels were kept to a minimum, with average dimensions of 2 m in height and 1 m in width (Rosenbaum, 1989). Tunnel width was also planned in accordance with local fracture geometries, with lithological variation showing strong control over fracture geometry and orientation (White, 2007). For example, the white chalk of the Seaford Chalk Formation exhibited typical sub-vertical and sub-horizontal fracture networks, while the Lewes Nodular Chalk Formation featured characteristics such as conjugate fracture sets and slickensided fracture walls (illustrated in Figure 3). The majority of subways and major tunnels are located within the Lewes Chalk, and occasionally they are found within Seaford Chalk. Deeper fighting tunnels, used to detonate explosives under forward enemy positions were also mostly located in the deeper Lewes Chalk (Figure 3, see also White, 2007).

The fracture patterns within the Seaford Chalk and Lewes Chalk have also played an important role in the long-term stability of

FIGURE 6: Image showing one of the Allies fighting tunnels near Vimy Ridge. Image credit: Labattblueboy - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=3871867>

the tunnels. The battle occurred more than 100 years ago, and over that century, weathering and dissolution has rendered most of the tunnels inaccessible. Fractures provide conduits for meteoric water dissolution, weakening tunnel walls and ceilings. Shelling during the battle itself created additional fractures and even collapsed some of the tunnels. Even to this day, this creates a potential hazard at the surface for both tourists and surface infrastructure (Deiderichs and Hutchinson, 2020).

GEOPHYSICS AT VIMY RIDGE:

It wasn't just the Allies who were able to exploit the chalks to create tunnel systems. The Germans were also advancing underground toward the Allies, which was of great concern to Allied operational planning. The first geophones were invented for these purposes and would be placed against excavation walls to detect enemy movement (Rosenbaum, 1989). These listening devices could accurately detect German mining up to 100 m away (Boire, 1992).

One innovative soldier, Counter Battery Officer Andrew McNaughton, started to develop improved methods to identify key enemy targets using geophysical methods. He brought in additional scientists to assist in developing new sound ranging and flash spotting methods to triangulate enemy cannons and provide more accurate targets for counter-battery fire (Gendzwill, 2007).

THE BATTLE:

Before dawn on April 9th, Easter Monday, 15,000 Canadian soldiers, the initial assault wave, gathered covertly in subways, shell holes, and trenches. The cold pre-dawn air and hardened muddy substrate were exacerbated by snow and sleet, concealing them from the enemy's view.

At 5:30 a.m., Allied artillery thundered, commencing the assault. The Canadians advanced behind the relentless artillery barrage, shielded by 150 well-placed machine guns. By late afternoon on that same day, three of the Divisions achieved their objectives on schedule, and pushed back the German front nearly 5 Km.

However, things were not as successful for the 4th Division. Just minutes into the assault, the 4th Division faced withering fire, suffering heavy casualties. Confusion reigned, and Hill 145 and the Pimple remained unclaimed by nightfall. The next day, aided by 4th Division reserves, renewed attacks secured Hill 145. Two days later, on April 12th, the Pimple fell after an intense battle in the snow. This marked an unmatched Allied advance on the Western Front, showcasing Canadian resilience and securing their historic victory at Vimy Ridge (see Foot, 2006 for more detail on the battle).

MEMORIALS:

The Canadian National Vimy Memorial, located in France, honors Canadian Expeditionary Force members who perished during World War I and serves as a tribute to Canadian soldiers from the same conflict without known graves in France (Figure 7). Situated within a 100-hectare battlefield park, it stands at the heart of the terrain where the Canadian Corps launched their initial assault during the Battle of Vimy Ridge.

The construction of the memorial, designed by Walter Seymour Allward, spanned eleven years. King Edward VIII unveiled it on July 26, 1936, in the presence of French President Albert Lebrun and a crowd exceeding 50,000, including 6,200 attendees from Canada. Following a comprehensive multi-year restoration effort, Queen Elizabeth II re-consecrated the monument on April 9, 2007, during a ceremony marking the 90th anniversary of the battle.

Initially, Allward wanted to use white marble for the memorial's exterior, but was advised against it, citing concerns about marble's suitability for the northern French climate. Instead, Allward embarked on a two-year journey to locate stone that possessed the right color, texture, and resilience (Hucker, 2007). He discovered it amidst the ruins of Diocletian's Palace in Split, Croatia, where he noted the stone's enduring quality over time (Figure 7). His selection, the Cretaceous Seget Limestone, originated from an ancient Roman quarry near Seget, Croatia.

Another memorial is located in Waterton National Park, in Southern Alberta. A mountain previously referred to as Goat Mountain was renamed as Vimy Peak, to honour those who fought in the battle of Vimy Ridge. The geologic history of this mountain and the surrounding area can be divided into 3 main phases: 1) Deposition of the Belt-Purcell Supergroup, 2) Mountain Building, and 3) Glaciation and subsequent surficial processes. The Belt-Purcell Supergroup was deposited approximately 1.45 Ga, and despite its great age, has not been metamorphosed. The result is a colorful blend of reddish-brown to green mudstones, light grey limestones, and tan-grey dolomites. Stromatolites are commonly found within Waterton Park, albeit not commonly within the strata of Vimy Peak.

Vimy Peak consists of stacked thrust faults, resulting in thrust-repeated successions of Altyn Formation, Appekunny Formation, and Grinnell Formation (Figure 8). This deformation is the product of mountain building that started ~165 Ma (Mudge and Earhart, 1980), with the

FIGURE 7: A) The Canadian National Vimy Memorial, located at the battleground in France. B) Diocletian's Palace in Croatia, which uses the same Seget limestone as the National Vimy Monument.

FIGURE 8: A) Photograph of Vimy Peak as seen from the Prince of Wales Hotel near the Bear's Hump trailhead. B) Annotated photo of Vimy Peak, showing approximate location of major thrusts in red, and unit boundaries in yellow (see Gordy et al., 1977).

Lewis Thrust being the major detachment surface under Vimy Peak. The strata of the Belt-Purcell Supergroup were carried to the northeast on the Lewis Thrust for approximately 140 km, before reaching their final location around 58 Ma. Pleistocene glaciation was then responsible for carving the mountains of Waterton into their current morphology. The resulting majestic beauty of this mountain serves as a reminder of the stalwart nature of the forces who fought in the battle of Vimy Ridge.

REFERENCES AND SUGGESTED READINGS:

- Cook, T. The Battle Of Vimy Ridge, 9-12 April 1917. <https://www.warmuseum.ca/the-battle-of-vimy-ridge>
- Deiderichs, M., Hutchinson, D.J. (2020). Tunnel Warfare in World War I: The Underground Battlefield Tunnels of Vimy Ridge, France. Published in *Tunnels and Underground Cities: Engineering and Innovation Meet Archeology, Architecture and Art*, Volume 1. p. 52-61.
- Doyle, P. (2014). Geology and the war on the Western Front, 1914–1918. *Geology Today*. Vol. 30, No. 5. Pages 183-191.
- Foot, R. (2006). Battle of Vimy Ridge. *The Canadian Encyclopedia*. www.thecanadianencyclopedia.ca
- Gendzwill, D. (2007). Vimy Ridge and Geophysics. *CSEG Recorder*, June 2007, Vol. 32 No. 6.
- Hucker, J. (2007). The Meaning and Significance of the Vimy Monument. In Hayes, Geoffrey; Iarocci, Andrew; Bechthold, Mike (eds.). *Vimy Ridge: A Canadian Reassessment*. Waterloo: Wilfrid Laurier University Press. pp. 279–290. ISBN 978-0-88920-508-6.
- Hutchinson, D.J., Diederichs, M., Pehme, P., Sawyer, P., Robinson, P., Puxley, A., Robichaud, H. (2008). Geomechanics stability assessment of World War I military excavations at the Canadian National Vimy Memorial Site, France. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*. Vol 45, No. 1, P. 59-77.
- Rosenbaum, M.S. 1989. Geological Influence on Tunnelling Under the Western Front at Vimy Ridge. *Proceedings of the Geologists' Association*. 100 (1). Pp. 135 – 140.
- Tucker, E.M. and Wright, V.P. 1990. *Carbonate Sedimentology*. Blackwell Scientific Publications., London, Great Britain.
- White, M.C. (2007). Geologic Controls on Instability in WWI Excavations, Canadian National Memorial Site, Vimy, France. Thesis. Queens University.